

Conductometric Study of Silver-Picolonic Acid Complex

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Picolonic acid has been reported to form complexes with alkaline earth metals¹, thallium², zinc, copper, manganese, cobalt³, and lead⁴ salts. The present investigation deals with the reaction between picolonic acid and silver ions in which a yellow gelatinous complex is formed which breaks up with time and the precipitate settles down, leaving a clear supernatant liquid after keeping overnight.

Silver nitrate and picolonic acid used were of B. D. H. AnalaR and chemically pure quality, respectively.

A Surfass conductivity bridge (3965) Model R. C. M. 15 B. L. and a platinised conductivity cell (cell constant 1.38) of the dipping pattern (Phillips) were used for conductance measurements, the temperature being maintained at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in a Gallenkamp thermostat.

The reaction was studied by Job's method⁵ of continued variation for measurements of conductance of the supernatant liquid, as shown by Joshi and Bhargava⁶, using reactants $5 \times 10^{-3} M$, $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$, and $2.22 \times 10^{-3} M$ in strength (Fig. 1, curves A, B & C respectively). In Fig. 1, curve D & E, the concentrations were $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ $AgNO_3$ and $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ picolonic acid and $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ $AgNO_3$ and $2.22 \times 10^{-3} M$ picolonic acid respectively. The plots show a peak at 1:1 stoichiometry of the complex.

Application of the monovariation method, using each of the reactants of strength $3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $2.22 \times 10^{-3} M$, confirmed the above observation (Fig. 2, curve B).

FIG. 1

$3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $2.22 \times 10^{-3} M$, confirmed the above observation (Fig. 2, curve B).

1. Robinson and Scott, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1932, 88, 417.
2. *Gium. Gazzetta*, 1924, 54, 204.
3. Becherescue, *Chem. Abs.*, 1960, 54, 24068.
4. Duval, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1950, 4, 159.
5. *Ann. chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113.
6. *This Journal*, 1963, 1, 19.

The total volume of the mixture, both in the continuous and monovariation methods, was kept at 10 ml.

FIG. 2

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Conductometric Study of Complexes of Picrolonic Acid with Co(II), Tl(I), Cu(II), Pb(II), Ba(II), Zn(II), and Mn(II) Salts

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In continuation of our work on complexes of picrolonic acid with the metal silver¹, a study of conductance of mixtures of picrolonic acid and some metal salts, mentioned below, has been undertaken which confirms the complex formation between Co (II), Cu (II), Pb (II), Ba(II), Zn(II), or Mn (II) and picrolonic acid in the ratio 1:2 and with Tl (I) in the ratio 1:1.

CoSO₄·7H₂O, Tl₂SO₄, CuSO₄·5H₂O, Pb(NO₃)₂, BaCl₂·2H₂O, ZnSO₄·7H₂O, and MnSO₄·7H₂O used were of B.D.H. AnalaR quality. The reagent picrolonic acid (B. D. H.) was chemically pure.

The experimental set up was the same as in the preceding note¹.

1, This issue, p. 241.

The reactions were studied by applying the monovariation method², using solutions of the metal salts and picronic acid of strengths mentioned below. The total volume of all mixtures was kept at 10ml. For each metal complex, three sets of each of the direct and the reverse titrations were carried. The observed conductance was plotted against the volume of the variable component and a clear break was found at the required stoichiometry of the complex. The conclusions are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

Salts.	Conc. of the salt soln.	Conc. of picronic acid.	Metal: picronic acid at the inflection.
Cobalt sulphate	$1.00 \times 10^{-2} M$	$3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$	1 : 2
	6.66×10^{-3}	3.33×10^{-3}	1 : 2
	1.25×10^{-3}	2.50×10^{-3}	1 : 2
Thallous sulphate	3.33×10^{-3}	3.33×10^{-3}	1 : 1
	1.11×10^{-2}	2.22×10^{-3}	1 : 1
	6.66×10^{-3}	2.22×10^{-3}	1 : 1
Copper sulphate	1.66×10^{-3}	1.66×10^{-3}	1 : 2
	1.11×10^{-3}	1.11×10^{-3}	1 : 2
	3.33×10^{-3}	1.11×10^{-3}	1 : 2
Lead nitrate	3.33×10^{-3}	1.11×10^{-3}	1 : 2
	1.66×10^{-3}	1.11×10^{-3}	1 : 2
	1.11×10^{-3}	1.11×10^{-3}	1 : 2
Barium chloride	3.33×10^{-3}	1.11×10^{-3}	1 : 2
	2.22×10^{-3}	1.11×10^{-3}	1 : 2
	1.66×10^{-3}	1.11×10^{-3}	1 : 2
Zinc sulphate	3.33×10^{-3}	1.11×10^{-3}	1 : 2
	2.22×10^{-3}	1.11×10^{-3}	1 : 2
	1.66×10^{-3}	1.11×10^{-3}	1 : 2
Manganese sulphate	3.33×10^{-3}	1.11×10^{-3}	1 : 2
	1.66×10^{-3}	1.11×10^{-3}	1 : 2
	1.11×10^{-3}	1.11×10^{-3}	1 : 2

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